

Name of Publisher: GO GREEN RESEARCH AND EDUCATION
Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review
Area of Publication: Business, Management and Accounting (miscellaneous)

Journal of Business and Management Research

Online ISSN

Print ISSN

2958-5074

2958-5066

Vol. 4, Issue. 3, 2025

Balancing Innovation and Ethics: A Systematic Literature Review of AI Applications, Ethical Challenges, and Mitigation Measures in the Public Sector

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Abstract

The technology of artificial intelligence is growing at a fast pace, emerging with new possibilities as well as challenges related to governance and ethical oversight. The primary focus of this systematic literature review is to observe how artificial intelligence is being utilized in the public sector and monitor its ethical concerns. This study investigates the relationship between governance and innovation, keeping ethical concerns in view. It also provides measures that can be taken by the government to minimize challenges and enhance effectiveness. The study utilized 'Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses' (PRISMA) approach from the year 2018 to 2024 by using Web of Science database and review of a wide range of the latest scholarly articles. The results of this review highlight opportunities while listing possible threats and providing intuitive information to politicians, practitioners, researchers, and other parties involved in defining the direction of AI technology.

Key Words: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Innovation, Technology Development, Ethical Oversight, Governance, Policy Recommendations, Systematic Literature Review (SLR).

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence technologies are moving forward at an incredible rate, changing a wide range of fields, economic sectors, traditional practices, and industries (Wirtz et al., 2021). However, they also bring forward several challenges, specifically related to governance and ethical oversight. Looking at this fast-paced proliferation of artificial intelligence in public sector governance calls to investigate ethics-related challenges, thus creating a balance between technological advancements and ethical implications (Abbas et al., 2025). A systematic literature review was conducted in this study to identify the areas of public sector governance, artificial intelligence technologies being used, and the challenges during their development and deployment (Henman, 2020).

AI governance can be defined as the frameworks and laws made to ensure that AI technologies have been implemented in a sound, open, and ethically responsible manner. Effective AI governance becomes crucial in the presence of challenges such as violation of data privacy, decision-making bias, and other unforeseen negative impacts (Bolton et al., 2021)). This study was guided by several important research questions. The first goal is to comprehend AI applications in the public sector. This entails figuring out in what ways artificial intelligence is used in public sector. The second area of study is structures and programs that can be implemented to raise AI systems' transparency and accountability by examining the challenges in its implementation.

Another significant subject that this research deals with is the measures that governments undertake to overcome the ethical challenges of AI implementation in the public sector (Auld et al., 2022) by systematically analyzing a thorough range of scholarly articles. Moreover, this review aims not only to add to the body of knowledge but also to offer practical and useful suggestions for individuals engaged in the management, creation, and governance of artificial intelligence technology. Artificial intelligence can be described as the conception of computer systems that are able to perform activities that usually require human intellect (Lemke et al., 2024). The tasks performed by artificial intelligence include reasoning, learning, perception, problem solving, language comprehension, and decision making. AI systems possess the ability to interpret complex data, adopt changing circumstances, and carry out tasks independently without human intervention in a way that mimics the cognitive processes of which only

human minds are capable of (Wirtz et al., 2020).

Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies consist of multiple arrays of algorithms, approaches, and techniques such as robotics, deep learning, machine learning, expert systems, natural language processing, and computer vision (Wirtz et al., 2021). Furthermore, the evolution of artificial intelligence started with the notion of Turing machine and machine intelligence, and Turing's work established a theoretical framework for artificial intelligence. His landmark work *Computing Machinery and Intelligence* (1950) presented the Turing Test as a standard to judge whether a machine is capable of intelligent behavior. Adding to Turing's work, Allen Newell, Herbert Simon, John McCarthy, and Marvin Minsky are regarded as inventors of artificial intelligence. McCarthy has been recognized as the father of artificial intelligence (AI) since he created the phrase and arranged the Dartmouth Conference in 1956. Minsky, Simon, and Newell (Minsky, 1970) significantly contributed to early AI research, including the invention of symbolic AI and problem-solving techniques. Feigenbaum and Lederberg: Feigenbaum and Lederberg pioneered the development of expert systems, artificial intelligence techniques that imitate the decision-making abilities of human experts in specific fields (Lederberg, 1990). They created the expert system Dendral for chemical analysis to demonstrate the practical applications of AI in specific sectors (Lederberg, 1990). Geoffrey Hinton, Yann LeCun, Yoshua Bengio, (LeCun et al., 2015). These researchers have made significant contributions to the field of neural networks and connectionism, which have been largely dormant since the 1960s.

Moreover, Hinton's seminal work on the development of deep learning architectures gave way to the emergence of neural networks in AI development. Taking on Hinton's work, Hopfield proposed a network that was capable of pattern recognition and associative memory which is also a type of recurrent neural network. Bengio (2015) advanced this research into machine learning, particularly in reinforcement and deep learning. The work of these researchers has led to advancements in robotics, natural language, and computer vision. The Google File System (GFS) and MapReduce, other key technologies that enabled the processing of big data sets and analytics, were developed by Sanjay Ghemawat and Jeff Dean. The era of the AI renaissance, which came with a surge of AI research and application, came into play with the seminal work of Bengio, followed by Geoffrey, Hinton, and Fei-Fei Li. Their combined work has led to massive breakthroughs in speech recognition, natural-language understanding, and image recognition.

Public governance, as defined by Fukuyama, involves the creation and enforcement of regulations with reference to service delivery. The focus of this study is to combine governance and artificial intelligence by overcoming challenges and focusing on the secure and effective development and deployment of AI. The upsurge of AI applications comes with multiple challenges for the government, such as sustainable development and economic issues, including labor markets) (Canton, 2021) along with societal concerns about ethics, privacy, and safety surrounded by fairness and bias (Van der Linden, 2019). These concerns call for the deployment of transparent AI to gain public trust (Bryson & Winfield, 2017), along with a strongly implemented governance framework that can promote inclusivity and accountability (Wirtz et al., 2020). Such complexities of the public sector that include diverse stakeholders' interests (De Sousa et al., 2019), scrutiny, and regular oversight have become essential, which calls for

improved policy development and regulation to effectively address such concerns (Wang et al., 2023). This calls for a thorough empirical study, particularly published in the previous six years, that deals with new concepts and the body of knowledge that national and international governments need academic research and practitioner accounts to provide multiple instances of artificial intelligence in real-world applications. Additionally, the transition from conventional to AI-based management (Agbozo & Spassov, 2018) demonstrates the significance of relatively new AI technologies, as well as the applicability of AI research in government (Afzal et al., 2024).

The advancement of artificial intelligence is rapidly increasing in all sectors of society and has resulted in new opportunities and challenges. (Dunleavy & Evans, 2019). While looking at the fast pace of technological advancements, there is a dire need for governance policies and structures that can match this rapid pace. Artificial intelligence systems are planned in such a way that they can imitate human intelligence and perform cognitive functions by solving complex problems, but these things come up with potential threats to society and new complex challenges. There is a significant gap in the literature on how these technologies can be supported by policies that can bring a balance between technical advancements and ethical deployment (Munir et al., 2024).

This study focuses on determining the ways in which AI is being used in the public sector, looking at its threats or challenges, and measures that can be taken to control possible dangers and bring in effective governance by reviewing the existing literature (Paul, 2022).

Research Objectives

1. To systematically map the current applications and use cases of AI across diverse public sector domains and identify key areas of adoption and operational impact.
2. To critically analyze the primary ethical challenges, including issues of algorithmic bias, transparency, accountability, and privacy, that emerge from the implementation of AI in public services.
3. To evaluate the effectiveness of existing regulatory frameworks, policies, and governance models designed to mitigate ethical risks associated with public sector AI.
4. To synthesize the findings into a comprehensive framework that proposes actionable strategies for fostering responsible AI innovation while upholding ethical principles and public trust.

Research Questions

1. What are the predominant applications and functional domains of AI currently being deployed in the public sector?
2. What are the most significant ethical challenges (e.g., algorithmic bias, lack of transparency, and accountability gaps) arising from the use of AI in public service delivery?
3. How effective are current governance mechanisms, regulatory policies, and ethical guidelines in addressing the identified challenges of public-sector AI?
4. What governance framework can be developed to balance the drive for AI-driven innovation with the imperative of ethical accountability and public trust in the public sector?

2. Methodological Approach

The present study provides Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-

Analyses (PRISMA) to examine innovation and governance in the context of ethical AI development (Moher, 2009). The SLR located, gathered, assessed, and compiled the body of knowledge on the subject using a systematic procedure from 2018 to 2024. First, predetermined search phrases and criteria were used to search relevant databases such as Web of Science and Google Scholar. Different search filters have been used: artificial intelligence (topic) and public governance (topic). Retrieved from Web of Science Categories: Public Administration or Social Sciences Interdisciplinary or Management. Refined By: Web of Science Index: Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) or Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI). Refined By:

Web of Science Index: Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) or Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI). Refined By: Web of Science Categories: Public Administration. The probe used for searching the required literature is TS “Artificial Intelligence AND Public Policy,” PY= ("2019-2024"), DT=("Article") AND LA=("English"). “After retrieval, the articles were assessed for relevance to the research topic using keywords, abstracts, and titles. Subsequently, a full-text evaluation was conducted on the selected articles to determine their suitability for inclusion in the review, considering pre-established inclusion and exclusion criteria focusing on the field of study, topic of the chosen literature, study design, language, publication year, and type (Mu et al., 2022).

The quality and applicability of the articles included were evaluated. Finally, the results from the chosen literature were arranged and examined using data synthesis methods such as thematic analysis. By guaranteeing a thorough and systematic analysis of the body of knowledge on innovation and governance in ethical AI development, this SLR approach offers insightful information on the subject.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field: Studies should be from public sector. • Type of study: Studies should deal with AI and Public Governance • Topic: Records should contain the words “AI & Governance” in their title and/or abstract. • Publication year: Studies published during 2018 -2024 • Publication Type: studies should be reviewed from international peer reviewed journal articles from ISI Web of Science. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-English studies, as resources for translation, may be limited. • Review-based articles, books, book chapters, proceedings, dissertations, reports, and conference papers. • Irrelevant studies • Studies for which full text isn’t available

PRISMA Figure-01

3. Data Extraction & Synthesis

3.1 Journals and Countries

These articles were published in 26 journals. The distribution of publications in numbers was as follows: Data and Policy (5), Journal of European Public Policy (5), Policy and Society (5), Public Policy and Administration (5), Earth System Governance (2), International Journal of Public Administration (2), Public Administration Review (2), Public Management Review (2), and Review of Policy Research (2). Additionally, the combined findings of all records demonstrate that the number of studies has grown significantly over the years and continues to show an increasing trend: just four articles were published in 2019 (8%), five in 2020, nine in 2021 (10%), again five in 2022 (10%), while there were 21 articles written in 2023 (40%). Until May 2024, 12 articles (24%) were already published within the first five months of the year, which shows the growing number of research works in the particular field, claiming that although thorough

innovation research in the public sector has been overlooked in the field of innovation studies, it is now increasingly developed (Lægreid et al., 2011) (Abbas & Shahid, 2024).

Percentage of Articles Published Per Year

Figure| 02

Figure| 03

While looking at the countries where the related research has been conducted, the number of studies in the United States is eight, four in the UK, three in European countries, and the rest are conducted in Australia, the Netherlands, China, Germany 2 each and few cross-national. Many studies explicitly do not mention any specific country where the

research has been conducted. This implies that the USA/Anglo-perspective is crucial for examining innovation and transformation. These findings have significant ramifications when considering the institutional bias that has permeated several studies. It may also have an impact on the findings' external validity by raising doubts about their applicability in non-Western (e.g., China) or Western (e.g., Europe) contexts.

Percentage of Studies Conducted by Country

Figure| 04

Number of Studies Conducted in Different Countries

Figure| 05

Table 2: Descriptive; Authors' Name, Country and Publication Year

S.#	Author Full Names	Country	Publication Year
1	Henman, Paul	Australia	2020
2	Robles, Pedro; Mallinson, Daniel J.	United States	2023
3	Li, Yiran; Fan, Yinging; Nie, Lin	China	2023
4	O'Shaughnessy, Matthew R.; Schiff, Daniel S.; Varshney, Lav R.; Rozell, Christopher J.; Davenport, Mark A.	United States	2023
5	Wirtz, Bernd W.; Weyerer, Jan C.; Sturm, Benjamin J.	N/A	2020
6	Wirtz, Bernd W.; Langer, Paul F.; Fenner, Carolina	N/A	2021
7	Djeffal, Christian; Siewert, Markus B.; Wurster, Stefan	22 countries including European Union	2022
8	Tan, Evrim; Jean, Maxime; Petit; Simonofski, Anthony; Tombal, Thomas; Kleizen, Bjorn; Sabbe, Mathias; Bechoux, Lucas; Willem, Pauline	Belgium	2023
9	Radu, Roxana	UK	2021
10	af Malmborg, Frans; Trondal, Jarle	Nordic countries	2023
11	Auld, Graeme; Casovan, Ashley; Clarke, Amanda; Faveri, Benjamin	N/A	2022
12	Young, Matthew M.; Bullock, Justin B.; Lecy, Jesse D.	United States	2019
13	Paul, Regine	Norway	2022
14	Koskimies, E.; Kinder, T.	Finland	2024
15	Dunleavy, Patrick;	globally	2023

16	Margetts, Helen Valle-Cruz, David; Garcia-Contreras, Rigoberto; Gil-Garcia, J. Ramon	N/A	2023
17	Simonofski, Anthony; Tombal, Thomas; De Terwangne, Cecile; Willem, Pauline; Frenay, Benoit; Janssen, Marijn	Belgium	2022
18	Taeihagh, Araz	Singapore.	2021
19	Schiff, Daniel S.	United States	2024
20	Bullock, Justin B.	N/A	2019
21	Moon, M. Jae		2023
22	Gaozhao, Dongfang; Wright, James E., II; Gainey, Mylah K.	United States	2023
23	van Noordt, Colin; Medaglia, Rony; Tangi, Luca	European Countries	2023
24	Bolton, Mitzi; Raven, Rob; Mintrom, Michael	N/A	2021
25	Newman, Joshua; Mintrom, Michael	Netherlands	2023
26	Schiff, Kaylyn Jackson; Schiff, Daniel S.; Adams, Ian T.; Mccrain, Joshua; Mourtgos, Scott M.	United States	2023
27	Yukhno, Alexander	N/A	2024
28	Castelnovo, Walter; Sorrentino, Maddalena	Italy	2021
29	Bell, Andrew; Nov, Oded; Tandon, Julia Stoyanovich	New York USA	2023
30	Wang, Yi-Fan; Chen, Yu-Che; Chien, Shih-Yi	Omaha, Taiwan	2023
31	Schmager, Stefan; Groder, Charlotte Husom; Parmiggiani, Elena; Pappas, Ilias; Vassilakopoulou, Polyxeni	Norway	2024

		Asia (Singapore and Japan), Americas (US and Canada), Europe (Germany and UK), and Oceania (Australia and New Zealand)	
32	Makasi, Tendai; Tate, Mary; Desouza, Kevin C.; Nili, Alireza		2021
33	Landon-Murray, Michael; Mujkic, Edin; Nussbaum, Brian	United States	2019
34	Dunleavy, Patrick, Evans, Mark	Australia	2019
35	Nitzberg, Mark, Zysman, John	Germany and the United States	2022
36	Ulnicane, Inga; Knight, William; Leach, Tonii; Stahl, Bernd Carsten; Wanjiku, Winter-Gladys Pillai, Vishnu	European Union and the United States	2021
37	Sivarudran; Matus, Kira J. M.	N/A	2020
38	Lemke, Nicole; Trein, Philipp; Varone, Frederic	Germany	2024
39	Hartley, Kris	Hong Kong	2024
40	Laux, Johann; Wachter, Sandra; Mittelstadt, Brent	N/A	2024
41	Mugge, Daniel	European Union	2024
42	Kruk, Sake R. L.; Kloppenburger, Sanneke; Toonen, Hilde M.; Bush, Simon R.	Netherlands	2021
43	Corcoran, Mary; Albertson, Kevin	United Kingdom	2024
44	Ulnicane, Inga; Aden,	United	2023

	Aini	Kingdom Europe, North America, and Asia, as well as big emerging economies like China, India, and Russia	2023
45	Papyshev, Gleb; Yarime, Masaru		
46	Pencheva, Irina; Esteve, Marc; Mikhaylov, Slava Jankin	N/A	2020
47	Schiff, Daniel S. S.	United States	2023
48	Khanal, Shaleen; Zhang, Hongzhou; Taeihagh, Araz	United States and Europe, UK and the European Union.	2024
49	Lawless, Christopher		2024

3.2 Data Extraction

We examined the goals of the chosen studies (Table 2), the journals in which they were published, the years of publication, and the databases used to locate them as part of this study. The majority of research is exploratory. Although 56 publications were initially found during our literature search, 49 articles were finally included in the list that addressed the research questions. Data were extracted from our literature review using a spreadsheet to capture the metadata for each of the selected studies. Table 3 shows the metadata we gathered for the 49 chosen studies, which include descriptive data, approach-related data, quality-related data, public governance, and AI-related data. These metadata categories were derived from literature review questions to maximize coherence.

3.3 Research Methods Used

Looking at the methodology of the studies, it was found that the research was dominated by qualitative studies, 33 (66%). Of these qualitative studies, most are policy analysis, document analysis, case studies, interviews with stakeholders, comprehensive reviews of existing literature, gray literature, legislation, government reports, observations, surveys, online experimental surveys, and comparisons of national strategies. Seven (14%) were quantitative, using SEM, surveys, quantitative text analysis, discourse network analysis, and regression analysis. Out of 50, only two used the mixed method approach, and the rest did not mention any methodology followed.

Percentage Distribution of Methodologies Used

Figure| 06

Distribution of Methodologies Used in Studies

Figure| 07

3.4 Policy Fields

Looking at the policy field, 20 were from public administration and governance studies. Ten are in public service, nine in the public sector, two in quality control and fraud detection, two in law enforcement, one in the public service area of policy development and technology governance, one in public sector applications, regulation, data, human capital, private sector support, and international cooperation, one in judicial systems, one in environmental governance, 1 in domain in tax and social security, one in policy making and regulation, 1 in the area of criminal justice. By looking at these results, studies by concentrate on the US and UK local government levels and include some first results of the programs implemented by the government. Relatively few studies have

been conducted on welfare and education.

Figure| 08

Figure| 09

Table 3: Data Analysis

S. #	Category	Metadata	Description
1	Descriptive information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Article number • Author’s full name • Article title • Source Title • Language • Document type • Keywords • Abstract • DOI (digital object identifier) • Publication Date and year • Country and city of research • WOS categories • Sample size • Document type • Publisher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study number assigned in excel workbook • What are authors’ full names? • What is the complete title of the article? • What is the source title of the article? • What is the language of the article? • What is the type of document? • What are the key words of the article? • What is the abstract of the article? • What is complete DOI of the article or the website? • What is the publication date and year of the study? • What is country of research and publication city? • In which web of science category, does it fall? • What is the sample size taken by the study if mentioned? • What is the type of document (for example article)? • What is the name of publisher? • What is the methodology, qualitative/quantitative/mix method?
2	Approach related information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research methodology 	
3	Quality related information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality concerns 	Whether any quality concern exists in study (for example limited information on methodology) listed as blanks

4	Public governance and AI related information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage of AI in public sector • Main challenges in deploying AI • Measures that government can take to overcome ethical challenges • Area of public research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In which areas AI is being used in the public sector? • What are the ethical challenges of AI implementation in the public sector? • What measures can governments undertake to overcome the ethical challenges of AI implementation in the public sector? • In which area of public sector, has the research been done?
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4. Data Analysis

Based on Table 3, data analysis was the last phase of our investigation. Initially, we conducted a methodical analysis of the unprocessed data obtained from the previously mentioned literature research process and documented our conclusions in Excel sheet reporting and ultimately used Section 4 (public governance and AI-related information) of Table 3, which provides answers to our research questions. Thematic analysis of all related information was performed to identify codes and then group them into themes (Clarke & Braun, 2017).

5.1. AI Applications in the Public Sector

1. Enhancing Citizen Services

1. Chatbots and Virtual Assistants

According to (Taeihagh, 2021) service delivery to citizens has improved through chatbots and virtual assistants that are driven by AI and are being extensively used by government organizations. Responding to inquiries, offering information, supporting, and providing residence excess to public services online, AI solutions provide accessibility and enhance user experience. For example, chatbots assist with a variety of queries from complicated bureaucratic procedures to provide answers to simple questions regarding public services. This reduces the human workload and expedites public service delivery.

2. Smart Cities

Smart city initiatives incorporate artificial intelligence technologies to enhance urban living circumstances. Applications include trash management, energy efficiency, traffic control, and public safety improvements. Artificial Intelligence reduces travel times and their impact on the environment by optimizing traffic flow, predicting congestion, and improving public transit systems. AI-powered energy management systems also minimize waste and optimize energy use (Yukhno, 2024). AI is also used in transportation systems for traffic controls, public transportation routes, forecasting traffic bottlenecks, shorter commute times, and offering optimal routes.

2. Data Driven Governance

1. Predictive Analytics

Data analysis is another outcome of AI technology, which can be used to predict certain outcomes based on previous records. Predictive analytics can be used to foresee possible hazards, disasters, and opportunities in public health trends and environmental concerns, thus utilizing resources optimally through decision-making (Young et al., 2019). Certain illness breaks can be predicted by looking at the current situation and relating it with the previous analysis in a short time; crime rates and areas can also be estimated, and preventive actions can be taken.

2. Enhanced Governance

Advanced artificial intelligence analytics facilitates data-driven policymaking by streamlining administrative procedures, decision support systems, and boosting compliance efforts. The use of AI can improve operational efficiency, minimize governance-related delays by optimizing workflows, and formulate policies by automating recurring jobs using complex information (Robles & Mallinson, 2023). In addition to helping decision-makers make sense of massive volumes of data, AI-driven systems also analyze and assess the effects of policies.

3. Ensuring Public Safety and Integrity:

1. Public Safety and Security

AI solutions provide improved safety and security to the public. Artificial intelligence systems can use real-time data analysis to identify trends in criminal activity, spot disinformation campaigns, monitor cyber security threats, and propose laws in areas where drug safety oversight and financial fraud detection are required (Simonofski et al., 2022). AI systems are used to predict probable crime areas, providing support to law enforcement organizations so that they can distribute their resources more efficiently to stop crimes before they occur using predictive policing. Emergency response systems are also improved using AI systems by enhancing coordination during emergencies, disaster management, recommending evacuation routes, anticipating natural disasters, optimizing resource allocation, and analyzing previous data to predict and prevent hazards.

2. Fraud Detection

Artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms play a critical role in identifying fraudulent activities in areas such as governmental procurement, social security benefits, and tax compliance. Artificial intelligence (AI) systems can detect irregularities and trends suggestive of fraud by examining vast amounts of data, which helps to avoid misappropriation of public funds and guarantees adherence to rules (Simonofski et al., 2022; Tan et al., 2023). AI makes it possible to enhance human capacity for managing intricate tasks. An example is the use of AI fraud detection to safeguard government data. The analysis used in contact tracing during the COVID 19 pandemic is a fairly recent example of augmenting AI-based public service support (Wirtz et al., 2020).

4. Revolutionizing Decision-Making Processes

1. Automated Decision-Making

Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are being extensively used in the public sector for automated decision-making processes, such as policy formulation, risk assessment, and resource allocation, to increase their accuracy and efficiency. Moreover, AI helps reduce biases and errors by eliminating human intervention in daily decision-making. Useful areas include welfare benefit distribution, where with the help of AI, more consistent and equitable enforcement of law becomes possible. According to (De Sousa et al., 2019), “it would likely increase citizen satisfaction,” and it “would facilitate connectivity and interactivity while reducing administrative burdens”

5.2. Challenges in deploying AI

1. Guardian of Justice; Ensuring Accuracy and Fairness in AI Algorithms

The first significant challenge discussed in the literature is avoiding biased outcomes arising from AI algorithms. AI governance must address this issue to minimize the chances of unintended consequences. AI systems are based on given data for processing instructions. If the data provided are biased, it will result in discrimination against a specific group, race, gender, and so on. The elimination or reduction of biased treatment challenges in AI systems must be tested extensively before their application. This can be done with two possible measures: establishing fairness standard criteria and including bias detection systems (Simonofski et al., 2022; Tan et al., 2023).

2. The Digital Fort Knox; Data Privacy and Security

The biggest challenges associated with the inclusion of AI in governance systems are data privacy and security concerns. AI-based systems often require personal information from users, which causes a sense of insecurity and raises privacy concerns. The issue is who has access to personal data and who can use it or misuse it. Data privacy laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in European countries, are a major step forward in setting standards addressing data privacy issues. The uniformity of these laws is critical for security. The guarantee of addressing privacy and security issues is possible through clear guidelines, safe storage of data, blockchain technology, and safe data encryption (Castelnovo & Sorrentino, 2021).

3. The changing landscape; Job Displacement and Societal Impact

Technological advances have been praised without realizing their social impact. AI is extensively used for automation, replacing human beings who lose their jobs. Many individuals, particularly those employed to perform routine and repetitive tasks, have replaced AI-based automation systems. The societal consequences of AI deployment, including economic inequalities and unemployment, have increased. It is necessary to enhance the skills level of employees and assist them in performing new jobs that AI cannot perform. Scholars have also identified a few related issues, including transparency, loss of privacy, biased information, and job loss in public-sector institutions (Walz & Firth-Butterfield, 2019).

4. The Legal Labyrinth; Navigating Regulatory Complexities

The evolution of AI is progressing at a very fast pace, and it is almost impossible to develop a regulatory framework that matches the pace of AI development. In the absence of a legal framework, the legislator’s ability to quickly respond to the

regulation of artificial intelligence development is a big challenge. Law-making is a time-consuming process, and outdated laws are no longer able to handle complications related to AI. There is a need to develop regulatory frameworks that keep accountability, complexities, and moral standards in mind. Cross-border cooperation and global trends can help develop a sustainable regulatory framework for AI applications (Laux et al., 2024).

5. The Glass Box; Transparency and Accountability in AI Decision-Making

The role of stakeholders in the decision-making process is a key element of the governance system. Most scholars have addressed the issues of non-transparency, prejudice, and discriminatory practices of AI. The fact that AI systems are often called black boxes implies that stakeholders cannot take part in the decision-making process. It is imperative that the necessary adjustments happen to ensure accountability and transparency in the use of AI in decision-making. AI developers need to develop self-explanatory protocols to facilitate easy understanding (Bell et al., 2023).

6. Taming the Unknown; Potential Risks and Failures

Artificial intelligence is neither completely accurate nor secure. It has already been agreed that there are probabilities of threats and failures, which may result in biased responses and adverse social results. Comprehensive evaluations must be made to reduce this threat. The prevention of potential failures depends on their early detection of these potential failures. Such challenges can be alleviated by establishing procedures that can assist in the determination of such risks and implementing rapid actions to counter such risks (Laux et al., 2024).

5.3. Measures undertaken by government to overcome ethical challenges in public sector.

1. Building the Foundation; Establishing Robust Regulatory Frameworks

The presence of well-defined guiding principles is important for ensuring successful AI governance. Policy and rule makers ought to enact laws considering the advancements and capabilities of AI, particularly focusing on responsibility, information protection, and ethical applications. To be sure that AI systems are being better understood, and the outcomes and actions taken are being justified, the regulations should provide access to the openness standards as well. Transparency can potentially allow governments to guarantee the trust of the population and reduce risks, including prejudices and discrimination, which have been frequently linked to AI. Ethical principles should be implemented to address these social problems. Such proposals must address laws primarily enabling the safe and ethical implementation of AI and active frameworks to deal with invasions of privacy, discrimination, and bias. Applying such ethical models would enable consumers and developers to incorporate societal interests and their welfare at the forefront of their choices. Such rules would lead to a consensus on the application of AI at the international level, and it would be less difficult to ensure that the development of AI complies with international standards (Makasi et al., 2021).

2. Illuminating the Black Box; Enhancing Transparency and Explainability

Transparency is necessary to make AI systems responsible and trustworthy (Henman, 2020). Thus, such AI systems must provide decisive explanations of their decision-making processes and the way they work. This includes revealing the algorithms behind it and providing a great level of decision rationality along with the awareness

of general users. This enables users to access and understand the transparency of AI systems, thereby increasing their trust. Transparency requires proper explanation, and AI should be developed in such a way that it can explain its decisions and results. It is also possible that the transparency offered by empirical clarity in AI enables the identification and elimination of bias, thereby ensuring that the execution of AI systems is as error-free as possible.

3. Uniting forces; Promoting Cross-Sector Collaboration

Governments, corporations, academic institutions, and civil society organizations, among others, may have to collaborate to address the problem of AI governance. Together, these groups would then be able to spread their skills and experiences in order to provide holistic solutions. The involvement of governments and regulatory bodies is a positive way to develop such initiatives by establishing platforms to communicate and collaborate in resolving issues related to AI, such as security, privacy, and bias. Various stakeholder groups allow different opinions and views to be considered in the regulatory process (Dunleavy & Margetts, 2023). More equitable and just principles of AI laws can appear as an effect of such an inclusive strategy. Stakeholders can provide interesting information about the ethics and social consequences of artificial intelligence and thus can assist in drafting legislation that captures a broad range of societal norms. Some of these stakeholders are politicians, scholars, field experts, and civil society organizations. (Bell et al., 2023).

4. Anticipating the Future; Conducting Risk Assessment and Impact Analysis

Governments should conduct appropriate risk assessments and explore the impact of AI systems. AI might have potential impacts on the economy, society, and individuals, which should be taken into consideration in such assessments. The more aware people are of these issues, the more feasible it will be to make lawmakers mitigate the threats and ensure that AI is used in the most beneficial and least harmful ways (Laux et al., 2024). However, the impact of AI applications can be analyzed on a regular basis, and it can reveal some shocking results and possible areas of development. Governments should be able to create new legislation to address the issues posed by AI. This will enable them to keep track of artificial intelligence and evaluate its performance on a periodic basis, which will ensure that AI technology adheres to moral values and societal goals.

5. Empowering the Public; Fostering Education and Awareness

Informed decision-making is crucial in the public sector, particularly for awareness and empowering people at large. Currently, governments of present times are taking several measures to achieve these objectives. The use of AI technology for public awareness and informed decision-making is ever increasing in government organizations. The basic aim is to improve the efficiency of public sector organizations. Few studies have highlighted that the use of AI is valuable and effective for public awareness and informed decision making. Technology has many advantages and disadvantages at the same time (Hartley, 2024). The most significant concerns are related to the ethical aspects of AI use in the public sector, such as privacy concerns, cyber security, and data privacy. Relevant stakeholders can formulate better mechanisms and frameworks for using AI technology in the public sector for maximum advantages. The technical, legal, and ethical aspects are equally important. The development of an improved legal framework with consultations from

all stakeholders can certainly improve its utility in the public sector (Gaozhao et al., 2024).

6. Bridging Borders; Strengthening International Cooperation

This technology is now widely used across borders, making it easier for people to interact and work while sitting in different places. The chances of international cooperation and collaboration have increased more than ever before because of artificial intelligence usage. Governments play a crucial role in regulating AI use in international cooperation. A regulatory framework at the international level is essential for the ethical use of technology. These laws will provide a sense of security and protection to facilitate opportunities for international cooperation as well as protect human rights globally (Schiff, 2023).

6. Findings and Conclusion

The primary focus of this systematic literature review is to provide deep insights into AI applications in the government sector and associated ethical challenges. This technology is often employed without consideration of ethical concerns. Technology is viewed as a way forward to improve the services and efficiency of public sector organizations. AI technology is used to improve decision-making, analytics, public safety, and government policy. Undoubtedly, the use of technology has been effective in reducing the administrative burden of government officials. The US use of AI has provided many options for people to access government services. forms of AI chatbots and virtual assistance. The concept of smart cities across the globe is possible owing to AI applications.

The potential of AI to facilitate all stakeholders is undeniable; at the same time, the use of AI poses serious challenges to governments because of ethical concerns. Scholars of various articles have highlighted such concerns. It is an emerging field in many countries that requires more research and careful attention before being used in any organization. The societal impact needs to be studied and addressed before employing AI in the public sector. Violations and breaches of people's personal domains are not acceptable. The safety and privacy concerns of people are equally important and need to be protected at any cost. Efficiency and effectiveness should not be the sole criteria for using AI in the public sector. Finally, it is a significant challenge for policymakers and the government to evolve a framework regarding the use of AI in the public sector while addressing the ethical concerns of all stakeholders.

References

- Abbas, N., Sadiq, S., Author), S. M. (Corresponding, Aziz, S., & Faheem, K. (2025). MAPPING OF DIGITAL GOVERNANCE RESEARCH: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF TRENDS, THEMES, AND GLOBAL COLLABORATIONS (2000–2025). *Contemporary Journal of Social Science Review*.
- Agbozo, E., & Spassov, K. (2018). Establishing Efficient Governance through Data-Driven e-Government. *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance*.
- Auld, G., Casovan, A., Clarke, A., & Faveri, B. (2022). Governing AI through ethical standards: Learning from the experiences of other private governance initiatives. *Journal of European Public Policy*.
- Abbas, N., & Shahid, M. S. (2024). *Mapping the Impact of Green Finance on Corporate Sustainability: A Bibliometric Analysis*. 4(1).

- Afzal, M. A., Munir, S., Abbas, N., & Farooq, A. (2024). A Retrospective of Earnings Management: Bibliometric Analysis. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 10(2), 253–272.
- Bell, A., Nov, O., & Stoyanovich, J. (2023). Think about the stakeholders first! Toward an algorithmic transparency playbook for regulatory compliance. *Data & Policy*.
- Bolton, M., Raven, R., & Mintrom, M. (2021). Can AI transform public decision-making for sustainable development? An exploration of critical earth system governance questions. *Earth System Governance*.
- Bryson, J., & Winfield, A. (2017). Standardizing ethical design for artificial intelligence and autonomous systems. *Computer*.
- Canton, H. (2021). Organisation for economic co-operation and development—OECD. In *The Europa Directory of International Organizations*.
- Castelnovo, W., & Sorrentino, M. (2021). The Nodality Disconnect of Data-Driven Government. *Administration & Society*, 53(9), 1418–1442. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399721998689>
- Clarke, V., & Braun, V. (2017). Thematic analysis. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*.
- De Sousa, W. G., de Melo, E. R. P., Bermejo, P. H. D. S., Farias, R. A. S., & Gomes, A. O. (2019). How and where is artificial intelligence in the public sector going? A literature review and research agenda. *Government Information Quarterly*.
- Dunleavy, P., & Evans, M. (2019). Australian administrative elites and the challenges of digital-era change. *Journal of Chinese Governance*.
- Dunleavy, P., & Margetts, H. (2023). Data science, artificial intelligence and the third wave of digital era governance. *Public Policy and Administration*.
- Gaozhao, D., Wright, J. E., & Gainey, M. K. (2024). Bureaucrat or artificial intelligence: People's preferences and perceptions of government service. *Public Management Review*.
- Hartley, K. (2024). State-society relations and government technology: A survey of public awareness and communication in Hong Kong. *Data & Policy*.
- Henman, P. (2020). Improving public services using artificial intelligence: Possibilities, pitfalls, governance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Public Administration*.
- Lægreid, P., Roness, P. G., & Verhoest, K. (2011). Explaining the Innovative Culture and Activities of State Agencies. *Organization Studies*.
- Laux, J., Wachter, S., & Mittelstadt, B. (2024). Trustworthy artificial intelligence and the European Union AI act: On the conflation of trustworthiness and acceptability of risk. *Regulation & Governance*.
- LeCun, Y., Bengio, Y., & Hinton, G. (2015). Deep learning. *Nature*.
- Lederberg, J. (1990). How DENDRAL was conceived and born. In B. I. Blum & K. Duncan (Eds.), *A history of medical informatics*.
- Lemke, N., Trein, P., & Varone, F. (2024). Defining artificial intelligence as a policy problem: A discourse network analysis from Germany. *European Policy Analysis*.
- Makasi, T., Tate, M., Desouza, K. C., & Nili, A. (2021). Value-Based Guiding Principles for Managing Cognitive Computing Systems in the Public Sector. *Public Performance & Management Review*.
- Minsky, M. (1970). Form and Content in Computer Science (1970 ACM turing lecture). *Journal of the ACM*.
- Moher, D. (2009). Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses:

- The PRISMA Statement. *Annals of Internal Medicine*.
- Mu, Y., Liu, B., Chen, B., Zhu, W., Ye, X.-H., Li, H., & He, X. (2022). Evaluation of association studies and an updated meta-analysis of VDR polymorphisms in osteoporotic fracture risk. *Frontiers in Genetics*.
- Munir, S., Sadiq, S., Abbas, N., & Rasul, F. (2024). E-Governance Initiatives and Citizen Participation at Global Perspective: Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*.
- Paul, R. (2022). Can *critical policy studies* outsmart AI? Research agenda on artificial intelligence technologies and public policy. *Critical Policy Studies*.
- Robles, P., & Mallinson, D. J. (2023). Artificial intelligence technology, public trust, and effective governance. *Review of Policy Research*.
- Schiff, D. S. (2023). Looking through a policy window with tinted glasses: Setting the agenda for U.S. AI policy. *Review of Policy Research*.
- Simonofski, A., Tombal, T., De Terwangne, C., Willem, P., Frenay, B., & Janssen, M. (2022). Balancing fraud analytics with legal requirements: Governance practices and trade-offs in public administrations. *Data & Policy*.
- Taeihagh, A. (2021). Governance of artificial intelligence. *Policy and Society*.
- Tan, E., Jean, M. P., Simonofski, A., Tombal, T., Kleizen, B., Sabbe, M., Bechoux, L., & Willem, P. (2023). Artificial intelligence and algorithmic decisions in fraud detection: An interpretive structural model. *Data & Policy*.
- Van der Linden, M. (2019). The International Labour Organization, 1919–2019: An Appraisal. *Labor*.
- Walz, A., & Firth-Butterfield, K. (2019). Implementing ethics into artificial intelligence: A contribution, from a legal perspective, to the development of an AI governance regime. *Duke L. & Tech. Rev.*
- Wang, Y.-F., Chen, Y.-C., & Chien, S.-Y. (2023). Citizens' intention to follow recommendations from a government-supported AI-enabled system. *Public Policy and Administration*.
- Wirtz, B. W., Langer, P. F., & Fenner, C. (2021). Artificial Intelligence in the Public Sector—A Research Agenda. *International Journal of Public Administration*.
- Wirtz, B. W., Weyerer, J. C., & Sturm, B. J. (2020). The Dark Sides of Artificial Intelligence: An Integrated AI Governance Framework for Public Administration. *International Journal of Public Administration*.
- Young, M. M., Bullock, J. B., & Lecy, J. D. (2019). Artificial discretion as a tool of governance: A framework for understanding the impact of artificial intelligence on public administration. *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance*.
- Yukhno, A. (2024). Digital transformation: Exploring big data governance in public administration. *Public Organization Review*.